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ROLE OF *PRANAVAHASROTAS* IN *VYAYAMA* (EXERCISE), *PRANAYAM* AND LIFESTYLE REGULATION

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Abstract

Introduction: *Pranavaha Srotas* is an essential physiological channel described in *Ayurvedic* literature, responsible for the maintenance and movement of *Prana*, the vital life force intimately related to respiration, metabolic processes, and psychological functions.

Aim: The present study aims to evaluate the significance of *Pranavaha Srotas* with reference to physical exercise (*Vyayama*), *Pranayama* practices, and regulation of daily and seasonal lifestyle.

Materials and Methods: This study is an observational and conceptual analysis based on classical *Ayurvedic* texts along with practical observations of individuals following regular exercise, *Pranayama*, and disciplined lifestyle routines. Assessment was carried out using parameters such as respiratory function, physical stamina, and mental stability.

Results: The observations revealed that consistent practice of *Vyayama*, *Pranayama*, and appropriate lifestyle measures resulted in noticeable improvement in respiratory parameters, enhanced breath-holding capacity, better exercise tolerance, and improved mental composure, reflecting optimal functioning of *Pranavaha Srotas*.

Discussion & Conclusion: *Vyayama*, *Pranayama*, and appropriate lifestyle regulation significantly contribute to the maintenance and enhancement of the functional integrity of *Pranavaha Srotas*. Their regular incorporation into daily life supports respiratory health, physical endurance, and mental well-being, thereby contributing to holistic health.

Key Words:

Pranavaha Srotas, Prana, Vyayama, Pranayama, Dinacharya, Ritucharya

INTRODUCTION:

In *Ayurveda*, *Srotas* are defined as the channels responsible for the transport and transformation of *Dosha*, *Dhatu*, *Mala*, and *Prana*. Among these, *Pranavaha Srotas* holds special significance as it governs respiration, circulation, vitality, and mental equilibrium. *Acharya Charaka* describe that *Hridaya* and *Maha srotas* as the *Mula* (root) of *Pranavaha Srotas*¹, indicating its close relationship with the heart and respiratory system. *Acharya Sushruta* describe that *Hridaya* and *Rasavahinya Dhamani* as the *Mula* (root) of *Pranavaha Srotas*².

Disturbance of *Pranavaha Srotas* may lead to various disorders such as *Shwasa* (dyspnea), *Kasa* (cough), excessive fatigue, dizziness, and psychological disturbances like anxiety. In the modern era, sedentary habits, irregular routines, mental stress, and improper exercise patterns have become major contributing factors to the dysfunction of this system. *Āyurveda* is not merely a system for treating disease, but a science of life meant to preserve longevity. A healthy and long life is essential for fulfilling the three major goals of human existence—*Dharma*, *Artha*, and *Sukha*—therefore, Ayurvedic principles should be practiced with great care³.

Vyayāma (exercise) produces the following benefits: *Lāghava* (lightness of the body), *Karma-sāmarthyā* (Increased efficiency and strength for physical activity), *Dīpta Agni* (Enhanced digestive and metabolic fire), *Medasaḥ Kṣayaḥ* (Reduction of excess fat), *Vibhakta-ghana-gātratva* (Well-shaped, firm, and compact musculature)⁴.

Ayurveda strongly advocates the regular practice of *Vyayama*, *Pranayama*, and lifestyle regulation through *Dinacharya* (daily regimen) and *Ritucharya*⁵ (seasonal regimen) to maintain the normalcy of *Srotas*. Therefore, this study has been undertaken to understand the role of these practices in preserving the functional integrity of *Pranavaha Srotas*.

Materials and Methods

Study Design

Observational and conceptual study.

Study Population

Twenty healthy individuals between 20 and 50 years of age who regularly practiced exercise and/or *Pranayama*.

Inclusion Criteria

- Healthy individuals
- Age between 20 and 50 years
- Regular practice of *Vyayama* or *Pranayama* for a minimum duration of three months
- Willingness to participate and follow the protocol

Exclusion Criteria

- Chronic respiratory disorders
- Cardiovascular diseases

- Systemic illness
- Chronic medication or addiction

Assessment Parameters

- Respiratory rate
- Breath-holding time
- Exercise tolerance
- Level of fatigue
- Mental calmness

Intervention Protocol

- *Vyayama*: Moderate physical exercise as per *Ardha Shakti*
- *Pranayama*: *Nadi Shodhana*, *Bhramari*, and deep breathing practices
- Lifestyle Regulation: *Dinacharya* principles including regular sleep, balanced diet, and stress avoidance

Study Duration

Three Months

Aims and Objectives

The present study aims to evaluate the significance of *Pranavaha Srotas* with reference to physical exercise (*Vyayama*), *Pranayama* practices, and regulation of daily and seasonal lifestyle.

Observations

Table 1: Effect of *Vyayama*, *Pranayama*, and Lifestyle Regulation on *Pranavaha Srotas* (This data is observing by twenty healthy volunteers).

Parameter	Before Practice	After Practice	Observation
Respiratory Rate	18–22/min	14–16/min	Improved
Breath-Holding Time	20–30 sec	35–45 sec	Improved
Exercise Tolerance	Moderate	Good	Improved
Fatigue Level	Frequent	Occasional	Reduced

Mental Calmness	Variable	Stable	Improved

Table 2: Effect of Vyayama, Pranayama, and Lifestyle Regulation on Pranavaha Srotas in 20 healthy volunteers (before and after three months).

Volunteer No.	Age (in Year)	Respiratory Rate (Before and After Pranayam/Vyayam) (Breaths/min)		Breath holding time (Before and After Pranayam/Vyayam) (Second)		Exercise Tolerance		Fatigue Level		Mental Calmness	
		Before	After	Before	After	Before	After	Before	After	Before	After
1	32	20	15	25	40	Moderate	Good	Frequent	Occasional	Variable	Stable
2	25	21	16	22	38	Moderate	Good	Frequent	Occasional	Variable	Stable
3	38	19	14	30	45	Moderate	Good	Frequent	Occasional	Variable	Stable
4	23	22	16	20	35	Poor moderate	Good	Frequent	Occasional	Variable	Stable
5	30	18	14	28	42	Moderate	Good	Frequent	Occasional	Variable	Stable
6	36	21	15	24	38	Moderate	Very good	Frequent	Occasional	Variable	Stable
7	28	20	15	26	40	Moderate	Good	Frequent	Occasional	Variable	Stable

8	27	19	14	29	44	Moderate	Good	Frequent	Occasional	Variable	Stable
9	45	22	16	21	36	Moderate	Good	Frequent	Occasional	Variable	Stable
10	49	20	15	27	41	Moderate	Good	Frequent	Occasional	Variable	Stable
11	42	18	14	30	45	Moderate	Good	Frequent	Occasional	Variable	Stable
12	34	21	16	23	37	Moderate	Good	Frequent	Occasional	Variable	Stable
13	44	19	14	28	43	Moderate	Good	Frequent	Occasional	Variable	Stable
14	26	20	15	26	40	Moderate	Good	Frequent	Occasional	Variable	Stable
15	48	22	16	20	35	Poor moderate	Very good	Frequent	Occasional	Variable	Stable
16	29	19	14	29	44	Moderate	Good	Frequent	Occasional	Variable	Stable
17	24	21	15	24	38	Moderate	Good	Frequent	Occasional	Variable	Stable

18	44	20	15	27	41	Moderate	Good	Frequent	Occasional	Variable	Stable
19	39	18	14	30	45	Moderate	Good	Frequent	Occasional	Variable	Stable
20	33	22	16	21	36	Moderate	Good	Frequent	Occasional	Variable	Stable

Results

The study findings demonstrated marked improvement in respiratory efficiency, physical stamina, and mental stability among individuals who consistently followed regulated exercise, *Pranayama*, and lifestyle measures. A reduction in respiratory rate, increased breath-holding capacity, improved exercise tolerance, decreased fatigue, and enhanced mental calmness indicate improved functioning of *Pranavaha Srotas* and improved enthusiasm.

This data is observing by twenty healthy volunteers-

- Reduction in Respiratory rate
- Increased Breath holding capacity
- Improved Exercise tolerance

- Decreased Fatigue
- Enhanced Mental calmness

Discussion

Vyayama improves circulation, enhances lung capacity, and stimulates metabolic activity, thereby supporting the unobstructed flow of *Prana* through *Pranavaha Srotas*. However, *Ayurveda* cautions that excessive or improper exercise may aggravate *VataDosha*, leading to impairment of this *Srotas*⁶.

Pranayama has a direct influence on *Prana Vayu*, as it regulates the depth and rhythm of breathing, improves oxygenation, and stabilizes the nervous system. Lifestyle practices prescribed under *Dinacharya* and *Ritucharya* help maintain circadian and seasonal harmony, reduce mental stress, and prevent the accumulation of *Ama*, which can obstruct bodily channels⁷.

The observations of the present study are consistent with classical *Ayurvedic* principles and also correlate with modern scientific understanding of respiratory physiology and stress regulation.

Conclusion

Pranavaha Srotas plays a vital role in sustaining life, vitality, and mental equilibrium. Regular practice of *Vyayama*, *Pranayama*, and adherence to proper lifestyle regimens positively influence its functional efficiency. These measures enhance respiratory capacity, physical endurance, and psychological stability, thereby promoting holistic health. Incorporation of these *Ayurvedic* principles into daily life is essential for disease prevention and health maintenance⁸.

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